

FEATURES OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN SCHOOLS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article reveals the features of teaching the Russian language in schools of Uzbekistan, and also examines the conditions for the formation of a linguistic personality and the role of methodological science in the development of communication abilities.

Keywords: language, communication, speech, “linguistic personality”, methodology, teaching, bilingualism.

Modern linguistics considers language a possibility, speech a product, and communication an activity. Consequently, when teaching the Russian language, it is necessary to more specifically define the functions of the language, the nature of speech and the characteristics of communication. Based on these tasks, we can assume that the main goal of the language teaching process is the education of a “linguistic personality.”

“A linguistic personality” is a person who can correctly express his thoughts and adequately perceive someone else’s speech, regardless of the topic, place and time of conversation” [4, 20]. A student can become a linguistic personality not by accumulating knowledge about the Russian language, as previously thought. Of course, as you learn a language, you need to acquire a certain amount of theoretical knowledge, have a sufficient vocabulary, but, above all, master communication skills. It must be borne in mind that the communicative abilities of a linguistic personality are formed and developed only in the process of communication. Language serves as a tool of cognitive activity, a form of thinking and a means of its development. Without well-developed speech skills, without the ability to express one’s thoughts, quickly and correctly perceive someone else’s speech, it is impossible to study in a modern school, or to become a full-fledged member of modern society.

To solve its problems, the methodology selects the best options within the framework of the class-lesson system, a strictly limited number of lessons and the volume of educational material according to approved programs and textbooks using equipment - from notebooks and chalkboards to television, computers, projectors and electronic boards. Sometimes an opinion is expressed about methodology as an applied, practical branch of pedagogy, giving recommendations for teaching a specific subject, a specific topic. The technique really gives such recommendations, but it also has theoretical parts; practical solutions are based on the known patterns of the formation of grammatical concepts, mastery of speech, mastering writing and spelling, reading skills, intonation, and the studied difficulties and mistakes of students. The diagnostic and prognostic functions of the technique are based on the knowledge of patterns. It is known that speech in the native language is formed in a certain sequence. “Children master their native language through speech activity, through the perception of speech and speaking,” and the main condition of this process is the child’s communication needs, “from the very beginning, speech arises as a social phenomenon, as a means of communication” [7, 26-28].

When teaching a second language, one cannot ignore the fact that language acquisition begins with the formation of listening skills. After long training, the first indicators of

communication appear - elements of non-verbal communication. For a long time, the child reacts to what he perceives with the help of facial expressions and gestures, only after that the first words and expressions appear. It should be noted that in terms of the volume of information contained, these words are equal to the goals of the statement and perform certain communicative functions. Consequently, when learning a second language, the main difficulty is not understanding the structure of the language, but other factors. The methodology considers the activities of students and teachers as interaction, as joint work, as cooperation with the leading role of the teacher. Over the past two decades, Uzbekistan has paid close attention to the issues of teaching foreign languages. This is evidenced by the adoption of the Law "On Education", the National Program for Personnel Training and a number of subsequent documents, the resolution "On additional measures to improve the study of foreign languages", which created favorable conditions for the development of language teaching methods. At the present stage of development of society, the main task of methodological science is to educate an individual who strives for the maximum realization of his capabilities, is open to the perception of new experiences, and is capable of making informed and responsible choices in various life situations. To develop such a personality, it is necessary to teach communicative competence, consisting of speech, linguistic and sociolinguistic competence. Brought up in such conditions, the learner must ultimately reach a level defined as the level of "linguistic personality."

School teachers of the Russian language, teachers of Russian studies have been and remain the initiators of innovations in the training and education of young people. They are looked at as a model and followed by example. All this testifies to the presence of the spirit of the Russian language, which must be preserved and skillfully passed on to future teachers of the Russian language.

This spirit is expressed in the general culture of teachers of Russian literature, all those who speak Russian, manifested in their sincerity, hard work, outlook and many other positive qualities. Children master their native language long before entering school, and for the most part they begin to become acquainted with the second language, in this case Russian, when they enter school. At the same time, non-Russian children immediately find themselves in conditions of educational bilingualism, when they are simultaneously given knowledge and instilled skills in two languages - their native and Russian. All this determined the peculiarities of teaching the Russian language to students of the national school. Teaching the Russian language in an Uzbek school, like any other language, is the development of children's thinking, improving and enriching the expression of thoughts with new means. The process of learning a language at school is a process of children learning new phenomena of reality. Therefore, the teaching of the Russian language in secondary schools is combined with the study of language, speech, and cultural materials covered by the content of training. When teaching Russian as a second language, two main goals were pursued: informative (implementation of information about language) and practical (formation of skills in the main types of speech activity - listening, speaking, reading and writing). The basis for teaching Russian language methods in any national school is the interconnected study of oral and written speech as two main forms of speech activity. Firstly, mastery of oral and written speech occurs as a result of performing sequential interrelated operations; secondly, the exclusion of some form of communication not only impoverishes the pedagogical process, but also negatively affects the development of other types of speech; thirdly, the differences in the structure and functions of both forms of communication should not be underestimated. When teaching a second language, it

is necessary to model all the parameters and conditions for the formation of skills in all types of speech activity in the native language and strive to comply with these conditions in the formation of skills through material units of the second language. It will not be possible to achieve complete adequacy of the conditions, because by the time the child enters school he manages to master his native speech, “a means of understanding the surrounding world, planning action,” and with its help satisfies the emerging needs of communication. Further, if quite a long time is given to develop the necessary skills when mastering one’s native speech, then the process of learning a second language is strictly regulated. The attitude of educators - parents and teachers - to the successes and failures of their students also differs. When communicating in their native language, the child feels at ease and relaxed, and is not afraid to make mistakes. In fact, the elders teach him to speak not in the literal sense of the word, but only “correct speaking.” From this point of view, there is an obvious need to intensify the process of the initial stage of teaching a second language in order for students to quickly overcome the emerging psychological barrier, developing their confidence that their attitude to the surrounding reality can be expressed using the means of another language. At the same time, overcoming the psychological barrier is the main and decisive factor in learning a second language. Traditionally, learning a second language begins with the development of speaking skills, and the use of any language means is encouraged. As a result, children often answer questions during lessons, recite, retell what they heard, ask questions, etc., creating the illusion of full communication in Russian. When checking, it turns out that not all students who excelled in the lesson are able to talk about other topics or answer the same questions in a different interpretation. This situation is explained by the fact that we do not take into account the laws of mastering the native language. The child’s first words in his native language are the result of fairly long-term “exercises” on the perception and comprehension of speech units. Every word a child pronounces is “supported” by a significant number of words and sentences, the meaning of which he understands. In Russian language lessons, due to the lack of such support, students try to remember not the essence of the conversation, but the answer appropriate to a specific question. So, in order to develop truly communicative skills, the teacher must for a certain time be content with the fact that his student does not speak; although he correctly follows commands such as “stand up”, “sit down”, “go to the board”; then the child should be taught to use paralinguistic means of communication (facial expressions, gestures) and only after that can one expect that the child will begin to answer questions with the words “yes” or “no”, incomplete sentences, that is, to use true communication skills. The learning situations created by the teacher to a certain extent compensate for the students' needs for real communication. Visual aids are indispensable helpers in creating learning situations.

The goal of language teaching can be defined as a consistent solution of a system of tasks for the formation and development of speech skills in all types of speech activity. The sequence of the above tasks is determined by certain features of speech mechanisms, the violation of which can affect the final learning result. Learning a language with this approach to the issue means: - developing skills in listening and understanding speech in the target language; - instilling skills in confirming understanding using paralinguistic means of communication; - development of speaking skills; - literacy training. It is necessary to take into account that the named types of speech activity can only develop in the specified sequence. In Russian language learning programs of all times, attention was paid to both the development of the ability to understand Russian speech by ear and the ability to speak. Memorization processes are most typical in the case of

simultaneous use of different types of memory. It was believed that the consistent study of grammar and vocabulary of the Russian language plays a very important role in the national school. A good basis for this is the interrelated study of syntax and morphology. To select certain units of speech, it is necessary to analyze speech in the most typical life situations. The topics will mainly be general everyday life, school, socio-political and popular science, but semantic topics should be determined by the selection of linguistic lexical and grammatical material necessary to reveal the topic. The skills that are necessary to master coherent speech were listed in the programs in exactly the same way as in the Russian language programs for Russian schools. The close connection and interdependence of teaching foreign languages and intercultural communication are so obvious that they hardly require lengthy explanations. Every language lesson is a crossroads of cultures, it is the practice of intercultural communication, because every foreign word reflects a foreign world and a foreign culture: behind each word there is an idea of the world conditioned by national consciousness (again foreign, if the word is foreign). Increased demand required a change in the system and content of language teaching. Today, teachers of foreign languages, including the Russian language, have found themselves in the center of public attention: representatives of various specialties in science, culture, business, technology and all other areas of human activity demanded teaching languages as a tool of production. Naturally, one is less interested in theory and history of language - They need foreign languages for use in various spheres of society as a means of real communication with people from other countries.

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